

NON-LINEAR FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF DCB TESTING OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

We perform a micro-macro finite element analysis of the development of plastic deformations in DCB testing of a unidirectional thermoplastic matrix composite. The objective is to understand the mechanisms responsible for the experimentally-observed decrease of toughness relative to the pure matrix. We use the commercial finite element code SAMCEF to compute the complex stress and strain fields near the crack tip. On that basis, an estimate of fracture toughness is predicted numerically. Results are discussed for a glass-fiber reinforced amorphous PAA matrix. We find that the plastic zone is not restricted in size by the reinforcement. Indeed, its volume is nearly six times larger than for the pure matrix. Numerical predictions for fracture toughness show the same decrease than that observed experimentally.

1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of our work is to understand the transfer of fracture toughness between a thermoplastic polymer matrix and the corresponding unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite. Various aspects of Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of thermoplastic matrix composites have been reviewed in [9], [13], [14] and [2]. The mechanisms responsible for the low efficiency of translation of resin fracture toughness into delamination fracture toughness, which is observed for high toughness thermoplastics, are not well understood. Yee [14] has proposed a possible cause based on an hypothesized reduction of the size of the plastic zone due to the presence of the fibers.

In the present work, we wish to understand the decrease of Mode I fracture toughness observed experimentally by Goffaux [6]. Using the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test, Goffaux [6] reports a significant decrease in toughness between an amorphous polyarylamid (PAA) matrix ($G_{Ic} = 7075 \text{ J/m}^2$) and the unidirectional, glass fiber-reinforced, amorphous

PAA composite ($G_{Ic} = 2040\text{J}/\text{m}^2$).

In order to understand this decrease of toughness, we propose to investigate the impact of the reinforcement on the development of the plastic zone in DCB testing. We perform finite element simulations based on a micro-macro approach proposed in [5] and further developed in [3] and [4], to predict the development of the plastic zone in the DCB test for both the pure matrix and the composite. We find that the plastic zone in the composite has a complex, three-dimensional geometry that is not constrained by the reinforcement as assumed by Yee [14]. Moreover, the volume of the plastic zone is nearly six times larger in the composite than in the pure matrix. Finally, the macroscopic results allow us to compute an estimate of fracture toughness at crack initiation. The numerical results show the same decrease than that observed experimentally.

2 MICRO-MACRO FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

The finite element analysis is based upon a micro-macro approach proposed in [5], and further developed in [3] and [4]. This approach is illustrated in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Macroscopic and microscopic computational domains.

In a first *macroscopic step*, we study the complete DCB specimen by means of a two-dimensional plane-strain analysis, treating the material as homogeneous. This macro-analysis allows us to determine the displacement field at the boundary of a neighbourhood of the crack tip (the small rectangular zone in Fig. 1). These computed displacements are used as boundary conditions for a second *microscopic step*, where we compute the three-dimensional displacement and stress fields near the crack tip. Here, the matrix and fiber reinforcement are discretized separately, assuming perfect bonding at the fiber/matrix interface.

In both macro and micro-analyses, the matrix is modeled as an elasto-plastic material, using the Prandtl-Reuss-von Mises constitutive equation of incremental plasticity [8]. In the macro-analysis, the composite is assumed to be described by the anisotropic plasticity model developed by Hill [7]. We have discussed in [4] the application of this model to the composite under investigation. The non-linear, anisotropic shear and traction data needed by the model are obtained by means of a separate micro-mechanical finite element analysis,

wherein the fibres are treated as elastic materials, while the matrix is assumed elasto-plastic. This numerical simulation has been described in [4]. The material properties of the PAA matrix and the continuous glass fibers are also listed in [4]. Finally, the load data correspond to the experimental conditions reported by Goffaux at crack initiation [6].

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS: PLASTIC ZONE

3.1 MATRIX

Figure 2: Plastic zone close to the crack tip for the pure matrix.

For comparison purposes, we consider first the case of the pure matrix. Figure 2 shows the computed plastic zone (in black) near the crack tip. The (half) plastic zone has an oval shape contained within a rectangle $351\mu\text{m}$ long and $341\mu\text{m}$ high. It is confined to the neighborhood of the crack tip. These results are compared next to those obtained for the composite, with either the macroscopic or microscopic analyses.

3.2 COMPOSITE

Figure 3a shows, also in black and at the same scale as in Fig. 2, the plastic zone for the composite computed in the macroscopic analysis using Hill's model. The (half) plastic zone is contained within a rectangle $2925\mu\text{m}$ long and $1270\mu\text{m}$ high. It occupies nearly all the height of the DCB specimen.

Figure 3b and c shows the results of the microscopic analysis. (This three-dimensional simulation consumed about 30 CPU hours on a CONVEX C3820 vector computer.) Figure 3b shows the trace of the plastic zone (in black) in a plane indicated by the arrow, namely a plane going through the matrix. The plastic zone in that plane is confined to the neighbourhood of the crack tip and is contained within a rectangle of about $138\mu\text{m}$ long and $119\mu\text{m}$ high. This corresponds to a height of 7 fibers. Figure 3c shows the trace of the plastic zone, at the same scale as in Fig. 3b, in a plane going through the fibers. In that plane, the plastic zone occupies a large fraction of the computational domain and is enclosed in a rectangle of

3000 μm long and 1203 μm high. This corresponds to a height of 64 fibers (namely, almost the total height of the DCB specimen). Note that the two-dimensional plastic zone obtained in the macroscopic simulation for the homogenized composite (Fig. 3a) presents the same shape and the same dimensions as that observed in the plane going through the fibers in the microscopic simulation. Finally, the computed volume of the plastic zone in the composite is nearly six times larger than in the pure matrix.

4 COMPUTATION OF FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

4.1 MATRIX

In order to evaluate numerically the fracture toughness of the pure matrix, we adopt the J-integral concept due to Rice [11]. The J-integral is given by:

$$J = \int_{\Gamma} (W dy - T_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} ds) \quad (1)$$

where Γ is an arbitrary contour around the crack tip, W is the strain energy density, T_i are the components of the traction vector, u_i are the components of the displacement vector, and ds is the arc length measured along the contour Γ . The coordinate system is shown in Fig.1. In the present paper, we compute the J-integral from the macroscopic finite element solution.

Rice showed that the value of the J-integral is equal to the energy release rate for a linear or non-linear elastic material undergoing small strains under quasistatic conditions. Thus, the J-integral computed from a simulation with loading conditions corresponding to crack initiation gives an estimate of the critical energy release rate of the material, or equivalently, of the fracture toughness. For elastic materials, the value of the J-integral is path-independent for contours that are outside the zone of large strains (near the crack tip) or sufficiently far from the sample boundaries (where side effects prevail). Similarly, path-independence of the J-integral is also verified for an elasto-plastic material if there is no unloading. In this case, the material can be assumed to behave like a non-linear elastic solid.

The advantages of the J-integral concept are manifold. In particular, it can be applied to both linear and non-linear materials. Also, the path-independence property allows one to evaluate the J-integral along a contour that is sufficiently distant from the crack tip, i.e. where numerical accuracy is easier to achieve. The Equivalent Domain Integral (EDI) technique [10] is used in the commercial code SAMCEF [12] to compute the J-integral. It consists of replacing the Rice contour integral by a surface integral. The EDI approach has improved numerical accuracy properties relative to the standard approach.

Fig. 4 shows the plastic zone (in black) at the crack tip for the pure matrix, the finite element mesh and two typical contours used for evaluating the J-integral. Nearly the total height of the DCB specimen is shown. We have used 20 different paths, that are numbered from the crack plane downwards. Table 1 gives the EDI results for the 20 paths considered. The first path is enclosed in a region of large plastic strains; the J-integral value is thus meaningless in this case. Path-independence of the J-integral results is verified, however, for paths #3 to #9. They give about the same value of fracture toughness ($G_{Ic} \cong 5550\text{J}/\text{m}^2$).

Figure 3: Plastic zone close to the crack tip for the composite: (a) Macroscopic result: homogenized composite, (b) Microscopic result: Trace of the (half) plastic zone, in black, in the plane shown by the arrow, (c) in a plane going through the fibers.

Figure 4: Plastic zone, finite element mesh and two paths used to compute the J-integral (pure matrix).

After Path #9, side effects come into play and path-independence is lost.

In conclusion, the above computations give a fracture toughness estimate of $5550 J/m^2$ for the pure matrix. We believe that this value is more accurate than that reported in the experimental work of Goffaux (i.e. $7075 J/m^2$) [6]. Indeed, Goffaux made use of linear elastic fracture mechanics to reduce his experimental data, while the present work does take account of the non-linear behavior of the matrix.

Integration Path	$J(J/m^2)$	Integration Path	$J(J/m^2)$
Path #1	4831.8	Path #11	5339.2
Path #2	5435.6	Path #12	5255.1
Path #3	5501.9	Path #13	5162.4
Path #4	5560.2	Path #14	5065.4
Path #5	5580.3	Path #15	4967.7
Path #6	5598.1	Path #16	4872.6
Path #7	5616.9	Path #17	4782.3
Path #8	5524.9	Path #18	4714.3
Path #9	5486.9	Path #19	4620.6
Path #10	5410.9	Path #20	4563.8

Table 1: J-Integral results (pure matrix).

4.2 COMPOSITE

We have computed an estimate of the composite's fracture toughness on the basis of the macroscopic simulation results obtained at crack initiation, using Hill's model. In the current release of the SAMCEF software, this can be achieved indirectly by means of the Elemental Crack Advance method [1]. In that method, the energy release rate can be inferred from the rate of change in global potential energy due to an incremental change in crack length.

Performing two separate macroscopic simulations, one with crack length a , and the other with crack length $a + \Delta a$ (both with the same boundary conditions), the energy release rate is estimated as follows :

$$G = -\frac{\Delta U}{w\Delta a} \quad (2)$$

where U is the potential energy of the sample, and w is the sample width.

In addition to the initial macroscopic simulation for a crack length of $a = 48mm$ (see Section 3.2), we have carried out two additional simulations, with crack lengths $a + 100\mu m$ and $a + 200\mu m$, both with the same loading conditions corresponding to crack initiation. This provides us with two estimates for the fracture toughness. We have found, respectively, the values $1336J/m^2$ and $1329J/m^2$.

As for the pure matrix, the computed values are relatively far from the reported experimental result ($2040J/m^2$). Here again, as for the pure matrix, we should note that the experimental value is reduced using linear elastic fracture mechanics. On the other hand, we find numerically a similar decrease in toughness relative to the pure matrix as that observed experimentally. This encouraging result validates the macroscopic simulation.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Non-linear, micro-macro finite element simulations have been performed to predict the extent of the plastic zone appearing at the crack tip in DCB testing of a unidirectional, thermoplastic polymer composite. The results show that the plastic zone in the composite has a complex three-dimensional geometry that is very different from that obtained for the pure matrix. The plastic zone is found not to be constrained by the fibers. It extends several fiber diameters beyond the crack tip plane and its volume is nearly six times larger than in the pure matrix. Moreover, we have computed estimates of the fracture toughness from the macroscopic results. We observe numerically the same decrease of toughness relative to the pure matrix than that observed experimentally. The next step in this study of the mechanisms governing toughness of thermoplastic matrix composites should be the computation, from the microscopic results, of the energy dissipated in the plastic zone.

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